

Supplementary materials

Related to the manuscript submitted to *Progress in Organic Coatings* journal in July 2020

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Title: **Influence of artificial weathering on coated MDF pre-treated with FE-DBD plasma**

Research part: *3 Results and discussion – 3.4 ATR-FTIR spectra*

Fig. S1. The detected ATR-FTIR spectra of coated samples in the wavelength region between 400 cm^{-1} and 3050 cm^{-1} , recorded after different intervals of AAW.

Research part: 3 Results and discussion – 3.6 Changes in coating films microstructure and surface morphology

Fig. S2. Surface morphology of coated MDF before AAW and after 250 h of AAW, detected with CLSM. The dimensions of the analyzed spots are 2560 μm \times 2560 μm .

Fig. S3. surface morphology of scratching traces, induced on differently pre-treated coated MDF, detected with CLSM: (top row) before AAW and (bottom row) after 250 h of AAW. The dimensions of the analyzed spots are $2560 \mu\text{m} \times 2560 \mu\text{m}$.